

Re-evaluation of *Liberibacter* family placement

Warrick R. Nelson

Independent researcher, Christchurch, New Zealand

Warrick.Nelson@gmail.com

ORCID [0000-0001-6695-0533](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6695-0533)

Abstract

When originally described (Jagoueix et al. 1994), *Liberibacter* were clearly identified from the partial 16S rRNA gene sequence as belonging to the *Alphaproteobacteria* Class. This Class includes many species known to be pathogens or symbionts, especially within the order Rhizobiales (now Hyphomicrobiales). The first validly published *Liberibacter* species in 2014 placed it in *Rhizobiaceae*. Most publications, where the family is listed, regard *Liberibacter* species as members of the *Rhizobiaceae*. However, the 2005 publication creating a new family, *Phyllobacteriaceae* (now *Bartonellaceae*) included the genus *Liberibacter*, at that stage only under the provisional Candidatus status. Yet others doubt that *Liberibacter* is really a member of either of these families. The extreme reduction in the genome, common in obligate endosymbionts, has resulted in the loss of core genes and could skew alignments and therefore phylogenetic placement, thus most taxonomic reviews of these families exclude *Liberibacter*. This analysis uses full, or nearly full, 16S rRNA sequences to attempt a more definitive family placement. This re-evaluation confirms *Liberibacter* do not fit within either the currently recognised *Rhizobiaceae* nor *Phyllobacteriaceae* (*Bartonellaceae*). A new family, *Liberibacteraceae*, is indicated.

Introduction

Liberibacter ecology

Many species of the *Liberibacter* genus are associated with serious and widespread diseases of important crops, most notably commercial citrus, potato, tomato and carrot. The names Huanglongbing (HLB), Citrus Greening, Zebra chip (ZC) and Psyllid yellows are commonly given to the set of symptoms expressed in them. These symptoms are generally visually striking and often economically devastating (Munyaneza 2013, Bové 2014b).

The bacteria are noted as obligate symbionts/parasites within their alternating insect and plant hosts. The insect host, various species of psyllid, acquires and subsequently transmits the bacteria during phloem feeding. The bacteria can reproduce to high titres in the insects, colonising the entire insect following ingestion (Kruse et al. 2017). Evidence of pili- and flagella-like surface appendages on the bacteria have been reported, but apparently restricted to presence in the insect midgut (Cicero et al. 2016, Yao et al. 2016). Psyllid host gene expression associated with *Liberibacter* infection (Fisher et al. 2014), plus

Liberibacter biofilm formation within the insect host, further suggests that *Liberibacter* can also be regarded as an insect pathogen (Cicero et al. 2017).

Once the bacteria are present in the salivary glands, the psyllid is then instrumental in introducing the bacteria during plant sap-feeding, probably during exploratory phases of probing the plant when some saliva is introduced to the phloem elements (Cicero et al. 2017). In the plant host, the bacteria are restricted to phloem cells, where they are motile or simply move with the flow of sap within the phloem system (Andrade et al. 2019, Achor et al. 2020). They can therefore explore and colonise a plant entirely, given enough time, from the point of entry down to the roots and up to the topmost extreme of phloem, including into fruits and seed coats as they develop. A number of reviews cover this process and differences between the various species of *Liberibacter*, geographical ranges and host insects and plants (Bové 2006, 2014a, Munyaneza 2012, Nelson et al. 2013a, Haapalainen 2014, da Graça et al. 2016, 2022).

From first identification and naming (Jagoueix et al. 1994), *Liberibacter* species (Table 1) are recognised as being closely related to *Agrobacterium*, *Brucella*, *Bartonella* and *Afpia* species, members of the Rhizobiales (now Hyphomicrobiales). The order Hyphomicrobiales has many examples of symbionts and pathogens, although the ancestral species of this order is considered to have been a free-living bacterium (Wang et al. 2020).

Where do taxonomy and genetic markers fit into these multi-stranded management practices? Early on in the development of understanding of HLB of citrus crops, it became clear that two organisms were involved with different sensitivities to ambient temperature. These are the Asian and African forms, two different *Liberibacter* species (Laf and Las) (Table 1)(Jagoueix et al. 1997), and with different primary psyllid host species vectors. Thus it became possible to map the presence and spread of these *Liberibacter* species (Bové 2014a). The advent of identifying 16S haplotypes within Lso (Nelson et al. 2011, 2013b) provided a means of identifying geographic ranges, vector species and non-crop plant hosts for this species (Wen et al. 2013, Swisher Grimm et al. 2018, Mawassi et al. 2018, Sumner-Kalkun et al. 2020, Kenney et al. 2024). Similarly, 16S sequence variations describe haplotypes/subspecies of Laf (Nelson et al. 2015a, Roberts & Pietersen 2017) and Leu (Nelson 2015, 2022, Tannières et al. 2020).

National biosecurity measures require precise delimitation and means of identifying organisms for implementing regulation of phytosanitary measures (Munyaneza 2013, EPPO 2022) or select agent status in the USA (Callaway 2008). These processes require a good description and knowledge of the taxonomy, especially where there are extremely closely related or cryptic species, some of which may behave differently. In addition, the finer the detail we can determine for an organism on noting an incursion, the better the chances of identifying the likely source and mode of movement. For example, haplotype identity of Leu species in New Zealand weeds revealed the country source of the bacterium and thus the means of incursion, in this case as an accidental entry in an imported psyllid weed biocontrol agent (Nelson 2015, Fowler et al. 2021).

Table 1: Currently known Liberibacter species and short form name used in this analysis. The highly reduced genomes and GC% are typical of symbiont/pathogenic adaptations (Oakeson et al. 2014). For comparison, the genome length of Rhizobiaceae genera is commonly 6.0–8.0 Mb and chromosomal genome ~5.06Mb (Young et al 2006), often with a single circular chromosome and one or more plasmids (Kuzmanovic et al 2022).

Species	Short name	16S rRNA gene length	Genome length and GC%
* <i>Candidatus Liberibacter africanus</i> (Jagoueix et al. 1994)	Laf	1500	1.192 Mb 34.5% (Lin et al. 2015)
* <i>Ca. L. americanus</i> (Teixeira et al. 2005)	Lam	1483	1.195 Mb 31.12% (Wulff et al. 2014)
* <i>Ca. L. asiaticus</i> (Jagoueix et al. 1994)	Las	1506	1.23 Mb 36.5% (Duan et al. 2009)
* <i>Ca. L. unnamed</i> (Chambers et al. 2020)	Lbh	1479	1.41 Mb 37.3 % (Chambers et al. 2020)
<i>Ca. L. brunswickensis</i> (Morris et al. 2017)	Lbr	1501 (39 nt missing at 3' end, counted in total)	n.a.
<i>Ca. L. capsicum</i> (Kwak et al. 2021)	Lcap	Only a 402 nt 16S sequence has been published	
<i>Ca. L. caribbeanus</i> (Keremane et al. 2015)	Lca		n.a.
* <i>Liberibacter crescens</i> (Fagen et al. 2014)	Lcr	1482	1.504 Mb 35.4% (Leonard et al. 2012)
<i>Ca. L. ctenarytaina</i> (Thompson et al. 2017)	Lct		n.a.
<i>Ca. L. europaeus</i> (Raddadi et al. 2011)	Leu	1484 (21 nt missing at 5' end, counted in total)	1.33 Mb 33.5% (Frampton et al. 2018)
* <i>Ca. L. solanacearum</i> syn <i>Ca. L. psyllidauru</i> (Hansen et al. 2008, Liefing et al. 2009)	Lso	1504	1.26 Mb 35.24% (Lin et al. 2011)

* indicates that the full length 16S sequence is available.

Current taxonomic position

The first description of *Liberibacter* species (Laf and Las), with partial 16S sequences (Jagoueix et al. 1994), did not place *Liberibacter* into a family. But the included phylogenetic tree, largely to demonstrate the membership of the *Alphaproteobacteria* class, strongly implies they might fit within the *Rhizobiaceae*. This was subsequently stated clearly in the first reports of Lcr and Lam genomes (Leonard et al. 2012, Wulff et al. 2014). Valid publication of *L. crescens* (Lcr)(Fagen et al. 2014) therefore claims taxonomic precedence as all other species had, and currently retain, *Candidatus* status and thus are not validly published entities. This family placement is now common in many references (for example Cooper et al. 2014, Ramulu et al. 2014, Ma et al. 2023, Naranjo-Robayo et al. 2026).

A genome analysis comparing Las with example genomes from *Agrobacterium* and *Sinorhizobium* (*Rhizobiaceae*), *Bartonella* (*Bartonellaceae*) and *Bradyrhizobium* (*Nitrobacteraceae*) species demonstrates a high degree of orthologous genes (Kuykendall et

al. 2012). This placed *Liberibacter* firmly in the order Rhizobiales (now Hyphomicrobiales), and also close to the modern *Bartonellaceae* and *Rhizobiaceae* families.

However, the description of the new family *Phyllobacteriaceae* (Mergaert & Swings 2005), in Bergey's Manual of Systematic Bacteriology, with seven genera, included *Liberibacter* as one of these (Garnier 2005). The published phylogenetic tree positions *Liberibacter* species as a separate clade alongside members of the *Rhizobiaceae*. However, in the same 2005 edition describing the *Rhizobiaceae* there is a taxonomic comment "The new genus '*Liberibacter*' represents strains of the fastidious organism that is the pathogen of citrus greening disease. This organism appears to be relatively distantly related to *Rhizobium*" (Kuykendall et al. 2005). However, "the position of this group as a member of the *Phyllobacteriaceae* is uncertain" (Willems 2014).

The Bergey's Manual online continues to list *Liberibacter* within *Phyllobacteriaceae* (Garnier 2015). However, both the List of Prokaryotic names with Standing in Nomenclature ([LPNS](#)) (Freese et al. 2026) and Genome Taxonomy Database ([GTDB](#)) (Parks et al. 2022) note *Liberibacter* only within *Rhizobiaceae* (both accessed April 2026).

Thus placement of *Liberibacter* definitively into one Family has still not happened (Table 2), with *Phyllobacteriaceae* and *Rhizobiaceae* both recognised and formally published.

Table 2: Taxonomic position of the genus *Liberibacter*. Note that family placement is currently ambiguous in major references.

Domain – Bacteria (Woese et al. 1990)
Kingdom – Pseudomonadati (Göker & Oren 2024), formerly Bacteria.
Phylum – Pseudomonadota (Oren & Garrity 2021), formerly Proteobacteria (Stackebrandt et al. 1988) and purple bacteria (Gibson et al. 1979). All are gram-negative (Kerstens et al. 2006).
Class – <i>Alphaproteobacteria</i> (Garrity et al. 2005), previously effectively but not validly published. Formerly α -subdivision of Proteobacteria (Woese et al. 1984) and group I purple bacteria (Gibson et al. 1979).
Subclass – Caulobacteridae (Ferla et al. 2013).
Order – Hyphomicrobiales (Douglas 1957), formerly Rhizobiales (Hördt et al. 2020).
Family – <i>Liberibacter</i> are currently placed in two closely related families. <i>Phyllobacteriaceae</i> (<i>Bartonellaceae</i>) (EPPO 1998, Brenner et al. 2005, Garnier 2005, 2015) and also in <i>Rhizobiaceae</i> (Kuykendall et al. 2005, Fagen et al. 2014, Ramulu et al. 2014, EPPO 2020, Hördt et al. 2020, Kuzmanović et al. 2022, Naranjo-Robayo et al. 2026). <i>Liberibacteraceae</i> – <i>fam. nov.</i> this review.
Genus – <i>Liberibacter</i> (Fagen et al. 2014) for <i>L. crescens</i> with all the other species remaining recognised under Candidatus status. The genus was originally described as <i>Liberobacter</i> (Jagoueix et al. 1994), subsequently corrected grammatically to the current <i>Liberibacter</i> .
Species – currently 11 species have been noted by sequence alignments, not all named. Refer Table 1 for species listing.

Taxonomic reviews

The class *Alphaproteobacteria* comprises a very broad group of Gram-negative bacteria, often of agricultural, clinical or ecological importance. Parasitic/endosymbiont organisms are associated with many diseases of plants and animals, while nitrogen-fixing bacteria, especially *Rhizobium* (*Rhizobiaceae*) but also those in 6 other families, are closely associated with plants and play a critical nutritional role. As is common with endosymbionts, extreme genome reduction and GC% are characteristic (Oakeson et al. 2014), but also can prove problematic for resolving taxonomic discrepancies. Traditional phenological features of morphology, physiology and habitat often contribute to apparent discrepancies. This discord appears to be particularly prevalent within the *Rhizobiaceae*, *Phyllobacteriaceae* and *Bartonellaceae* families and a few closer relatives.

Alphaproteobacteria and Hyphomicrobiales

A taxonomic analysis of *Alphaproteobacteria*, using concatenated alignments of selected protein families, indicated two broad clades within the Rhizobiales (Williams et al. 2007). The first clade includes genera *Brucella*, *Bartonella*, *Mesorhizobium*, *Rhizobium*, *Sinorhizobium* and *Aurantimonas*. The second clade comprised *Rhodopseudomonas*, *Nitrobacter*, *Bradyrhizobium* and *Xanthobacter*. Another *Alphaproteobacteria* review and extension of new taxa, specifically noting potential systematic errors in previous analyses using multiple protein-coding genes, reverted to 16S rRNA gene but concatenating both small and large subunit (SSU and LSU) rRNA genes to provide better discrimination than possible with the SSU (16S) alone (Ferla et al. 2013). *Rhizobiaceae*, *Bartonellaceae* and *Brucellaceae* clustered closely, with *Phyllobacteriaceae* a little more distant. No genome for *Liberibacter* was yet available for these reviews.

The major review and whole genome analysis of the *Alphaproteobacteria* (Hördt et al. 2020), placed *Liberibacter* in a cluster with *Martelella* species (*Rhizobiaceae*). A review of the order *Hyphomicrobiales* using a combination of concatenated core genes and 16S sequences (diCenzo et al. 2024) simply noted *Liberibacter* in the family *Rhizobiaceae*, but since this genus lacks >10% of the core single genes used for this review, it was excluded from the analysis. However, their Supplementary S7 16S phylogenetic tree (trimmed genes) shows *Liberibacter* nesting most closely with *Limoniibacter endophyticus* (*Bartonellaceae*).

Phyllobacteriaceae (now *Bartonellaceae*)

Since the original 2005 description of the new family *Phyllobacteriaceae* (Mergaert & Swings 2005), the number of genera has increased from seven, including ‘*Candidatus Liberibacter*’ (Garnier 2005, 2015), to a total of 18 (Mustaq et al. 2024), but now making no mention of *Liberibacter*. The 2014 description of the *Phyllobacteriaceae* (Willems 2014) specifically notes *Liberibacter* as “associated with the family” and that membership of *Phyllobacteriaceae* is uncertain.

Rhizobiaceae

The phenological placement of species and genera within this family, with *Rhizobium* (meaning living in a root) as the type genus, was becoming strained as more genera were added to the family.

Although the phylogeny of this family is mostly supported by means of 16S sequences, there are anomalies that have caused considerable discussion (Yanagi & Yamasato 1993, van Berkum et al. 2003, Carareto Alves et al. 2014). In particular, symbiotic functions and the range of host plants can be markedly different to evolutionary associations based on the 16S gene (Carareto Alves et al. 2014). Thus other genome components have been used to resolve placement in the family. An early attempt compared phylogenies of *Rhizobiaceae* species using either 16S or 23S genes (van Berkum et al. 2003). Another compared 16S and *dnaK* genes (Eardly et al. 2005) from nine *Rhizobiaceae* type strains, thus not including *Liberibacter* in their analysis. Members of the *Rhizobiaceae* are particularly known to require more detail than simply a 16S sequence alignment to differentiate at species level, hence the many revisions of this family conducted over the years (de Lajudie et al. 2019).

A *Rhizobium* and close relatives review, using near full length 16S rRNA genes, separated *Rhizobiaceae* as a monophyletic clade, but close to *Bartonellaceae* and *Phyllobacteriaceae*, each in their own monophyletic clades (Young et al. 2001). *Liberibacter* is not mentioned as no genomes were available at that time.

Phylogenies using multi-locus sequence analysis, full genome sequences (core-genome), amino acid identities and various selections of core genes, alongside 16S sequences, resulted in a number of revisions and novel descriptions at family, genus and species levels (Wang et al. 2018, Kuzmanović et al. 2022, Ma et al. 2023, Naranjo-Robayo et al. 2026). Small genome size relative to other *Rhizobiaceae* (Table 1), with resultant lack of many of the 170 core genes targeted, resulted in *Liberibacter* being excluded (Kuzmanović et al. 2022). Low bootstrap support at genus and species level from 16S rRNA phylogenies prompted further review, but apart from noting *Liberibacter* as being validly published within the *Rhizobiaceae*, this species does not appear in their analysis (Ma et al. 2023). Using different tools but the same 170 core genes as (Kuzmanović et al. 2022), *Liberibacter* was again not included, other than noting valid publication as a member of the *Rhizobiaceae* (Naranjo-Robayo et al. 2026).

The (Ramulu et al. 2014) phylogeny, based on amino acid sequences of bacterial r-proteins, unambiguously placed *Liberibacter* within *Rhizobiaceae*. However, they noted *Las* and *Bartonella* clustering as being artefactual since they are “unrelated Rhizobiales”, noting that both are more closely related to *Sinorhizobium* (*Rhizobiaceae*) and *Brucella* (*Brucellaceae*, now *Bartonellaceae*) species.

Thus the broader phylogenetic placement of *Rhizobiaceae* families, genera and species offers no resolution for the placement of *Liberibacter* from these recent major re-analyses.

Nor is there clarity on whether *Liberibacter* is better placed with *Phyllobacteriaceae*. There is continued doubt that, apart from being closely related, *Liberibacter* should be placed in either *Phyllobacteriaceae* (*Bartonellaceae*) or *Rhizobiaceae*, in spite of authoritative publications. In particular, phylogenies based on genomes and protein-coding genes, rather than rRNA genes, commonly do not include endosymbiont species.

Molecular taxonomic tools

16S rRNA gene

The 16S gene has long been recognised as a reliable and useful taxonomic tool. It is a universally conserved rRNA gene and sequences are now readily and very widely available (Woese & Fox 1977, Woese et al. 1984, 1990). Its use has resulted in the ability to determine the broad outlines of the three major domains of life, “allowing most phylogenetic relationships (including the most distant)” (Woese 1987). It is now regarded as the optimum tool for taxonomic classification of the many unculturable, and especially obligate intracellular, organisms (Stackebrandt & Rainey 1995, Yarza et al. 2014). It is commonly called the “gold standard” of bacterial molecular phylogeny (Stackebrandt & Ebers 2006, Richter & Rosselló-Móra 2009, Bartoš et al. 2024).

Initially, it proved most useful to determine genus and family placements, subsequently including species determinations, especially as full length sequences became common. The generally accepted nucleotide similarity threshold on the 16S (full length sequence) gene to delineate a species is >98.2%, genus is 94.5% and family is 86.5% (Stackebrandt & Ebers 2006, Kim et al. 2014, Yarza et al. 2014, Rosselló-Móra & Amann 2015, Ramazzotti & Bacci 2018). The more recent analysis (Hackmann 2025) indicates broader, and slightly overlapping, ranges for delineation. Thus genus is 90.1-99.0%, family 72.9-90% and >97.2% at the species level. In some instances, within-species level identification has been possible, for example in describing haplotypes of *Liberibacter* species (Nelson et al. 2011).

A few specific circumstances have been demonstrated where further investigation is required when an anomalous placement is obvious. This may occur through very rare instances of 16S horizontal gene transfer and thus a complete break in the evolutionary links (Kitahara & Miyazaki 2013, Sevillya 2022, Bartoš et al. 2024). These circumstances suggest other genetic components should be considered.

Use of short read sequences, fairly common before longer reads became more readily available, has resulted in some databases indicating anomalous assignments to genera or families (Leducq et al. 2026). Confusion within the ‘*Rhizobiaceae* group’ has been longstanding (Yanagi & Yamasato 1993), partly because of phenotypic features not corresponding with 16S sequence phylogenies.

Genome and other methods

Alternative genetic tests have been developed to attempt to address cases where 16S rRNA gene analysis provides insufficient resolution or conflicts with phenotypic

diagnostics. These include multi-locus approaches, selection of conserved “core” genes and whole genome sequence. In particular, these are intended to resolve the incongruity of family placement of genera. However, core-gene and genome-based phylogenies can be problematic for organisms with markedly reduced genomes, which may lack many otherwise conserved metabolic genes. In addition, gene duplication and horizontal gene transfer can cause phylogenetic signals in some loci to diverge from 16S-based phylogeny (Doolittle & Brown 1994, Pace 1997).

Whole-genome and core-gene approaches may therefore have limited applicability for taxa with extreme genome reduction, where missing data are substantial and may bias placement. In such cases, near-full-length 16S rRNA gene analysis remains a robust and broadly comparable marker for genus- and family-level inference.

Methods

Full, or nearly full, length 16S sequences, primarily of type species, were downloaded from [NCBI](#) (National Centre for Biotechnology Information). The choice of species was all the *Liberibacter* species, most with full length 16S sequences (Table 1), plus selected members representing species or families regarded as showing close phylogenetic closeness, for example *Rhizobiaceae*, *Phyllobacteriaceae*, *Bartonellaceae*, and *Kaistiaceae*, plus some type species of many of the families recently included in the enlarged *Bartonellaceae* (diCenzo et al. 2024). The current family per [LPSN](#) (List of Prokaryotic names with standing), accessed April 2026, was added into the FASTA file in front of the genus name to show in the cladogram (Figure 1). Accession details and sequences are given in Appendix 1.

Sequences were first aligned for visual inspection in Clustal X v2.1 with NJ alignment method (Larkin et al. 2007). Nucleotides beyond the 5' and 3' ends were trimmed manually. Most species use the common start codons ATG or TTG (Suzek et al. 2001) and stop codon TAA (more common in low GC% genomes)(Korkmaz et al. 2014). Some type species had considerably truncated sequences and these were replaced by a close relative (same genus) with a full sequence. A few species have less than full length sequences available, generally <20 nucleotides missing at either or both ends, thus not including any of the taxonomically important variable regions. A few *Liberibacter* species only have shorter sequences available (Table 1). The default Clustal X and MAFFT terminal gap methods were applied.

Final alignment and guide tree were produced in MAFFT v7 (Kato & Standley 2013) using the on-line [EMBL-EBI](#) Job Dispatcher (Madeira et al. 2024) and the cladogram visualised using [ITOL](#) v6 (Letunic & Bork 2024), rooted to *Hyphomicrobium* (*Hyphomicrobiaceae*) as the outgroup, based on this family being a reasonable distance from *Bartonellaceae* and *Rhizobiaceae* (diCenzo et al. 2024). Rooting to a more distant species, such as *Wolbachia*, made the cladogram less easily read. A cladogram rather than phylogram has been used specifically to focus on the branching order to avoid confusion of

the implied evolutionary distance of a phylogram derived purely from 16S rRNA gene analysis (van Berkum et al. 2003).

Average nucleotide identity (ANI) with pairwise calculated differences (ANI%) was determined via the BLASTn tool of [NCBI](#). Representative species from genera historically regarded as closely associated with *Liberibacter* species were used.

Results and Discussion

Liberibacter species clearly form a monophyletic clade (Figure 1) with a sister polyphyletic clade comprising of species of *Aurantimonadaceae*, *Bartonellaceae*, *Devosiaceae* and *Rhizobiaceae*. This polyphyletic clade suggests that further taxonomic review of the families and species is warranted. *Nitrobacteraceae* form the next closest family. The same monophyly of *Liberibacter* species was demonstrated using both 16S and concatenated selected core genes (Fagen et al. 2014), but without any comment about family placement other than recognising *Rhizobiaceae*.

Figure 1: Cladogram of selected Hyphomicrobiales 16S rRNA gene sequences visualised with ITOL, *Hyphomicrobium* is the outgroup. *Liberibacter*s are represented by their 3-letter short form (Table 1) and Genbank code. The tree is a neighbour joining cladogram based on 1000 bootstrap replicates. Numbers at the branches indicate bootstrap support values, only values >170 are shown.

Apart from known instances of genomic heterogeneity within multiple 16S gene copies, for example *Rhizobium etli* and *R. galegae* (Young et al. 2004), taking advantage of the otherwise known reliability of (near) full length 16S sequence phylogeny to discriminate genera, and therefore also families, is arguably a useful approach to review these families.

Revision of *Rhizobium* and relatives using 16S rRNA genes confirmed the closeness of *Phyllobacteriaceae* and *Bartonellaceae*, but as monophyletic clades (Young et al. 2001). *Rhizobiaceae* are a sister monophyletic clade to *Phyllobacteriaceae*/*Bartonellaceae*, while

Brucellaceae form a clade separate again. This represents quite a difference to the cladogram here, even when some common species are represented. The 16S sequences in both cases are nearly full length (1440 nt for Young et al. 2001) which seems unlikely to cause these anomalies. Differences in tree topology methods, highlighted by them in their own different trees, plus family assignments in this analysis based on whole genome taxonomic treatments.

Genomic heterogeneity is strongly associated with six or more 16S copies (Větrovský & Baldrian 2013). In a review of genomic 16S heterogeneity in Proteobacteria, Firmicutes, Actinobacteria, and Bacteroidetes, similarity was 98.7-100% and noted remarkable homogeneity in the *Alphaproteobacteria* (Coenye & Vandamme 2003). Discordant phylogenies have nevertheless been reported within genera of some *Rhizobiaceae* (Yanagi & Yamasato 1993, van Berkum et al. 2003). However, this generally affects species relatedness, rather than genus or family levels (Young et al. 2004, Bartoš et al. 2024).

The species *Limoniibacter* and *Martellela*, which have been suggested as closer relatives of the *Liberibacters*, show no particular closeness over other members of the broader *Rhizobiaceae/Bartonellaceae* clade. *Liberibacter* clustering with *Martellela* (Hördt et al. 2020) based on whole genome analysis is not upheld by this 16S gene analysis.

The key point here is that the *Liberibacter* genus, while closely related to the broader *Bartonellaceae/Rhizobiaceae* grouping, is clearly a separate, monophyletic clade. This supports the earlier phylogenetic tree (Fagen et al. 2014).

Start codon usage for bacterial genes generally show ATG as the most common, TTG the least and GTG between them (Suzek et al. 2001). During visual inspection of 16S rRNA gene sequences, all available sequences used either ATG or TTG and no GGT. All *Liberibacter* species used ATG, but members of the *Bartonellaceae* and *Rhizobiaceae* used both. The more distant families all used TTG, including *Methylobacteraceae* and *Nitrobacteraceae*. This is a trivial difference from an alignment basis, but does suggest some evolutionary advantage to have developed and/or retained the higher energy requiring TTG version.

Table 3: Average nucleotide identity comparing 16S genes of Lcr or Lso against species from closely related families. Gene sequences are the same as used for the cladogram. ANI% determined via the BLASTn tool of NCBI. The most recent Family level ANI% difference is a minimum of 80.1-94.1% (Hackman 2025), previously 86.5-94.4% (Yarza et al 2014).

Genus	Family	ANI % Lcr	ANI% Lso
<i>Aurantimonas</i>	<i>Aurantimonadaceae</i>	89.96	87.60
<i>Limoniibacter</i>	<i>Bartonellaceae</i>	91.64	89.18
<i>Rhizobium</i>	<i>Rhizobiaceae</i>	92.53	89.53
<i>Kaistia</i>	<i>Kaisteaceae</i>	90.14	87.94

With ANI% differences (Table 3) between the key relative families all being less than 94.1%, the *Liberibacter* genus can clearly be regarded as belonging to a different family.

Using the overlapping ANI% difference categories (Hackmann 2025), *Liberibacter* could be argued, solely on this measure, as potentially belonging to the genera *Limoniibacter*, *Rhizobium* or *Kaistia*. Considering other taxonomic differences across these families, including life cycles and ecological factors, this is unlikely and unhelpful to clarify the family designation for *Liberibacter* and certainly not supported by the 16S analysis.

Where closely related species are not readily distinguished by the 16S gene sequence, whole genome analysis has been recommended (Chun et al. 2018). Genomic heterogeneity of 16S genes causing issues with phylogeny (Ueda et al. 1999, Sun et al. 2013) does not apply, as the three copies in *Liberibacter* species are homogenous (Nelson et al. 2015b). It is likely that *Liberibacter* species, as obligate dual plant/insect intracellular symbionts, have even more highly conserved 16S genes than perhaps is generally common, thus allowing 16S sequences to discriminate not only species but even to 16S haplotypes (Nelson et al. 2013b, 2015a, Viljoen et al. 2013, Swisher et al. 2017, Sumner-Kalkun et al. 2020).

The close association of many *Rhizobiaceae* with plants has sometimes been used as a reason for placing *Liberibacter* within the *Rhizobiaceae*. However, while *Liberibacter* species are typically known to be obligately intra-cellular in plant phloem, they are also obligately intra-cellular in their insect host. This is remarkably similar in many respects to *Candidatus* Phytoplasma species, that are also obligate intracellular organisms, also with alternating plant and insect hosts, and in many cases the plant symptoms are hard to distinguish from those of *Liberibacter* infection. Both genera also exhibit extreme genomic reduction and low GC%. However, phytoplasmas are extremely distantly related, sitting in the Phylum Mycoplasmatota (Firrao et al. 2004). The more closely related genus *Bartonella* are infectious in animals and also have small genomes and reduced GC% (Dahmana et al. 2020). Thus genome and lifecycle commonalities do not reflect an evolutionary genetic link, but rather common responses to an obligately intra-cellular lifestyle.

Placement of the currently only culturable (and therefore non-*Candidatus* *Liberibacter*) species into *Rhizobiaceae*, appears to be strongly influenced by the earlier assumptions of this family placement for other species (Fagen et al. 2014, Table 2). The small genome size and low GC% of the species do not support placement alongside *Rhizobium* species, while placement within the *Bartonellaceae* may be supported as the primary cellular fatty acid profile resembles these species, but not those of *Rhizobium* (Fagen et al. 2014). Similarly, the conclusive placement of *Liberibacter* into *Rhizobiaceae* by rRNA amino acid analysis, suggested as a new standard for prokaryotic systematics, is not supported by their own discussion of artefactual clustering (Ramulu et al. 2014).

Whole genome sequence and similar concatenated core gene phylogenies may be useful for species discrimination within a genus. The exclusion of *Liberibacter* in recent reviews, because of a large proportion of missing discriminatory genes within the greatly reduced genome, suggest that these techniques are not necessarily useful for outlier genera. More specifically, to place the much reduced and low GC% genome content typical of obligate intracellular organisms into a more general phylogeny, the current almost universally used

and long-standing full length 16S sequences remains the better distinguishing genetic marker, particularly at genus or higher level (Bartos et al 2024). Other genes may distinguish specific strains of a species, often useful for population and geographic discrimination. Examples of such genomic markers that discriminate populations within *Liberibacter* species exist (Bastianel et al. 2005, Chen et al. 2010, Haapalainen et al. 2018).

Conclusion

The 16S and ANI% measures both indicate that *Liberibacter* species are separate enough from these other families to justify placement within their own family as a member of the Hyphomicrobiales. They form a monophyletic clade, distinct from, but closely related, to the families *Aurantimonadaceae*, *Bartonellaceae* and *Rhizobiaceae*. A new family, *Liberibacteraceae*, is proposed.

Taxonomic proposal

Description of *Liberibacteraceae* fam. nov.

Li.be.ri.bac.te.ra.ce.ae (N.L. neut. n. *Liberibacter*; type genus of the family; *-aceae* suffix to denote a family; N.L. fem. pl. n. *Liberibacteraceae*, the family of the genus *Liberibacter*; from L. n. *liber*, bark and N.L. neut. n. *bacter*; a rod).

The description is as for the type genus *Liberibacter*. Members are rod-shaped; some species may be pleomorphic. Known species are associated with the phloem sieve tubes of plants and the haemolymph and salivary glands of insect vectors (Psyllidae). The DNA GC content of the type species is 35.3 mol% (determined from genome analysis). The family is distinguished from *Rhizobiaceae* and *Phyllobacteriaceae* by its specialized ecological niche as obligate pathogens/endosymbionts of alternating plant and insect hosts, by ANI% and by phylogenetic distance based on 16S rRNA gene sequences.

Type genus: *Liberibacter* Fagen et al. 2014.

Taxonomic Note: The family currently contains one validly published species, *Liberibacter crescens*. Other members of the genus *Liberibacter* currently hold 'Candidatus' status and are excluded from formal nomenclature under the ICNP until validly published, although they are phylogenetically consistent with this family assignment.

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Appendix 1

FASTA file of 16S rRNA gene sequences used in this analysis

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Devosiaceae|Devosia_riboflavina_IFO_13584_D49423 Root
here AACGAACGCTGGCGGCAGGCTTAACACATGCAAGTCAAGCAGCCCGCAAGGAGTTGGCAGACGGGTGAGTAAACGCTGGGAATCTACCTAGTTCTACGGAACAACAG
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Aurantimonadaceae|Aurantimonas_sp CP090066.1:444420-445902 Aurantimonas sp. HBX-1 chromosome, complete
genome CTGAGAGTTTGATCTGGGCTCAGAACGAAACGCTGGCGGCAGGCTTAACACATGCAAGTCAAGCAGCCCGC CAAGGGGAGTGGCAGACGGGTGAGTAAACGCTGG
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Nitrobaetereaceae|Bradyrhizobium_americanum__CMVU44_KU991833

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Rhizobiaceae|Ensifer_alkalisoli|CP034909.1 :c2554706-2553197 Ensifer alkalisoli strain YIC4027 chromosome 1, complete sequence

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Lafj|CP004021a.1a :c123884-122380 Candidatus Liberibacter africanus PTPSAP5Y, complete genome

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Lam|CP006604a.1a :c152273-150786 Candidatus Liberibacter americanus str. Sao Paulo, complete genome

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Las|CP001677a.5a :c418322-416812 Candidatus Liberibacter asiaticus str. psy62, complete genome

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Lso|CP002371a.1a :305984-307492 Candidatus Liberibacter solanacearum LSo-ZC1, complete genome

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Rhizobiaceae|Marteella_endophytica |HM800924.1 Marteella endophytica strain YC6887 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence

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Bartonellaceae|Phyllobacterium_meliloti strain T1293 chromosome, complete genome

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Bartonellaceae|Mesorhizobium_sp |CP033365.1:1799020-1800508 Mesorhizobium sp. NZP2298 chromosome, complete genome

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Rhizobiaceae|Mycoplana_dimorpha |EU022307.1 Mycoplana dimorpha strain DSM 7138 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence

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Rhizobiaceae|Sinorhizobia |AY875975 .1 Sinorhizobium sp. ORS3178 16S ribosomal RNA gene, partial sequence

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GAAGTCGTAACAAGGTAGCCGTAGGGGAACCTGCGGCTGGATCACCTCCTTTCTAA

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rium_tumefaciens NR_174322.1 Agrobacterium tumefaciens strain CNPSo 675 16S ribosomal RNA, complete sequence

TTGAGAGTTTATCTGGCTCAGAACGAACGCTGGCGCAGGCTTAACACATGCAAGTCGAACGCC CCGCAAGGGGAGTGGCAGACGGGTGAGTAACCGTGGGAATCT
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TCAGAACGAACGCTGGCGGACGGCTAACACATGCAAGTGAACGCCCTGGCAACAGGGAGTGGCAGACGGGTGAGTAACCGGTGGGAATCTACCTTGTGTACGGAACA ACCAAGGGAACCTTTGGCTAATACCGTATGAGCCCTTCGGGGAAAGATTATCGCCATAAGATGAGCCCGCTAGGATTAGCTAGTTGGTGGGTAATGGCTCACCAAGGC GACGATCCTTAGCTGGTCTGAGAGGATGACGAGCCACTGGGACTGAGACACGCCAGACTCCTACGGGAGGCGACAGTGGGGAATATTGGACAATGGGCGCAAGCCT GATCCAGCCATGCCCGCTGTGTGATGAAGGCCCTTAGGGTTGTAAGCACTTTCCGCCGATGAAGATAATGACTGTAGTCGGAGAAGAAGCCCGGCTAATCTCGTCCAGCA GCCCGGTAATACGAAGGGGCTAGCGTTGTTGGAATTACTGGGCGTAAAGCGTACGTAGGCGGATTGTAAGTGAAGGGTGAATCCCGAGGCTCAACCTCGGAAGTGC CTTTCATACTGGCAATCTTGTAGTCCGGGAGAGGTGAGTGGAACTCCTAGTGTAGAGGTGAAATTCGTAGATATTAGGAAGAACACCAAGTGGCGAAGGGGCTCACTGGCCC GAAACTGACGCTGAGTACGAAGCGTGGGAGCAACAGGATTAGATACCCCTGGTAGTCCACGCCGTAACCGATGGATGCTAGCCGTCGGGAGGCTTGTCTTCGCTGTCG CGCAGCTAACGCATTAAGCATCCCGCTGGGAGTACGGTGCAGATTAACCTCAAAGGAATTGACGGGGCCCGCACAAAGCGGTGGAGCATGTGGTTAATTGCAAGC AACGCGCAGAACCCTTACCAGCTTGTGACATGTACGATGGGTACCGGAGACGGTATTCTCAGTTCCGGCTGGCGTGAACACAGGTGCTGCATGGCTGTGCTGAGCTCGTG TCGTGAGATGTTGGGTTAAGTCCCGCAACGAGCGCAACCCCTGCCCTTAGTTGCCATCATTAGTTGGGCACTTAGGGGACTGCCGGTGAAGCCGAGAGGAAGGTG GGGATGACGCTCAAGTCTCATGGCCCTTACGGGCTGGGCTACACACGTGCTACAATGGCGGTGACAATGGCAGCGAAGGGCGACCTGAGCTAATCTCAAAAAACCTC CTCAGTTCCGATTGCACTCTGCAACTCGAGTGCATGAAGTTGGAATCGTAGTAAATCGTGATCAGCATGCCCGGTGAATACGTTCCCGGGCTTGTACACACCGCCGTC ACACCATGGGAGTTGGTTTTACCCGAAGGCGTGGCGCTAACCCAGCAATGGGAGGAGGCGCACCGTAGGGTCAAGCAGTGGGGTGAAGTCTGAACAGGTAGCCGTA GGGGAACCTGCGGCTG

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